

CURRENT STATUS OF PEDAGOGICAL CONDITIONS FOR DEVELOPING PROFESSIONAL TRANSVERSAL COMPETENCES OF FUTURE EDUCATORS

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Abstract. *The article discusses the current state of professional transversal competencies of future educators, the development of transversal competencies, and their necessity in pedagogical activity.*

Keywords: *future educator, transversal competence, development, communicative, analysis, critical thinking, innovative educational technologies, distance learning, e-learning systems, interactive educational materials, professional competencies of educators, communication, online collaboration, creative thinking, pedagogical team, the importance of practice.*

INTRODUCTION.

Nowadays, changes are taking place in the education system all over the world, which affect all aspects of pedagogical activity. The main goal of education is not only the transfer of knowledge, but also the development of general competencies of the individual, the formation of skills necessary for successful functioning in modern society. In this process, the professional competencies of teachers working with children are of particular importance. Professional training of teachers is not limited to pedagogical knowledge, but also requires the development of transversal competencies, such as social, communication and problem-solving skills.

In the Decrees of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan "On measures to further deepen reforms in the higher education system and bring it in line with international standards" dated July 29, 2020, "On additional measures to improve the quality of the education system, training of teaching staff and development of scientific research" dated December 18, 2019 and "On measures to further improve the higher education system" dated July 5, 2017, special attention is paid to the integration of higher education institutions into international education systems, the development of scientific research and innovative developments, the training and advanced training of teaching staff in the higher education system. It was adopted in order to develop new programs for the training of teachers and researchers of higher education institutions in accordance with advanced pedagogical and scientific methods, including the use of new methods and technologies in education, as well as in order to reform the higher education system and improve its quality. The decrees focus on the independence of universities and higher education institutions, integration into international education systems, modernization of educational programs, and the development of students' competencies in various fields.

In the modern education system, the requirements for teachers are constantly growing, so it becomes necessary to introduce future specialists to modern pedagogical methods and technologies, as well as to develop such skills as social responsibility, self-organization and problem solving. Therefore, it is very important to study the pedagogical conditions for the formation of professional transversal competencies of future teachers.

The article analyzes pedagogical conditions and modern pedagogical approaches to the formation of professional transversal competencies of future teachers. The importance of

innovative technologies, psychological and practical training, the development of social and moral responsibility in the pedagogical process, as well as related scientific and practical developments will also be discussed. The analysis carried out in the article allows us to demonstrate the effectiveness of pedagogical conditions aimed at forming professional competencies of teachers in accordance with modern requirements.

LITERATURE REVIEW

It is known that in the modern education system, the issue of forming transversal competencies in students and teachers is studied. There is a lot of literature devoted to the pedagogical foundations of the concept of "competence", one of which is education. When training teaching staff, especially educators, important conditions for the development of professional competencies are necessary. In her book "Pedagogical Competence: Theoretical Foundations" G.A. Strukova analyzes the development of professional competencies and transversal competencies of a teacher, methodological aspects of the educational process, psychological aspects of a teacher's professional growth. V.P. Slastenin's textbook "Pedagogy" presents comprehensive concepts for the formation of professional training and competencies of a teacher, which can serve as a basis for the development of general competencies of teachers.

Pedagogical innovations, especially the use of information technologies, play an important role in the formation of professional competencies of future teachers. Of these: N.A. Berkovich provides information on the development of innovative pedagogical technologies and effective approaches to teaching. In his opinion, distance learning and interactive teaching tools give effective results in the development of professional competencies of teachers. In her book "Innovative Pedagogy" V.P. Elnikova emphasizes the importance of new pedagogical technologies and the advantages of using innovative methods in training teachers and educators. This literature can be effectively used, especially in modernizing the pedagogical process.

Psychological and pedagogical training of teachers is an important factor in the formation of their professional competencies. Many scientific works have been written about the importance of pedagogical and psychological training: S.I. Golubev's book "Psychology and Pedagogical Training" examines the psychological and pedagogical aspects of preparing teachers for professional activity, as well as the formation of their relationships. In her work "Psychology and Education" T.A. Vinogradova explores psychological approaches to preparing teachers for social and professional life, contributing to the development of transversal competencies.

Practical and pedagogical experience is of particular importance in the formation of the necessary competencies in educational and upbringing activities. The role of practice in the training of teaching staff is great. Mudrik's book "Pedagogical Practice and Teaching Experience" examines ways and methods of effectively conducting pedagogical practice. This literature contributes to the development of practical skills of teachers. N.V. Kuzmin emphasizes the problems of practical work of teachers and the importance of practice in the development of transversal competencies.

There are scientific studies devoted to the social and moral responsibility of teachers, as well as the need to develop their teamwork skills and communicative competencies. A.A. Derkach's book "Social Pedagogy" discusses the importance of social pedagogy, as well as the social and moral responsibility of teachers. This literature is especially useful for developing the responsibility of future teachers to society.

In scientific work on the formation of professional transversal competencies of future teachers, pedagogical, psychological, social and ethical aspects are studied in a complementary manner. In these areas, there is a wide range of scientific approaches and practical results that will help to successfully develop the competencies of future teachers.

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY AND EMPIRICAL ANALYSIS

Pedagogical conditions for the formation of professional transversal competencies of future teachers are a very relevant topic today and include many factors that correspond to innovations, changes and modern requirements in the education system. Transversal competencies are skills that help develop not only knowledge and skills related to a specific profession, but also social, communication, problem-solving and self-organization skills necessary in everyday life and professional activities.

These days there are a number of pedagogical conditions for the development of professional transversal competencies of future teachers:

Improvement of pedagogical programs and curricula:

Training programs and courses are created to develop professional competencies of teachers. These programs include not only pedagogical knowledge, but also transversal competencies, such as communicative, analytical, creative and critical thinking.

Innovative educational technologies:

The use of modern information technologies, distance learning, e-learning systems, interactive educational materials is of great importance in the development of professional competencies of teachers. These technologies also stimulate communication, online collaboration and creative thinking.

Importance of the teaching staff and practice:

The practical work of teachers and educators should allow them to solve problems arising in their profession and apply innovative approaches. Practice and pedagogical experience are the most effective ways to apply theoretical knowledge in practice.

Promotion of human rights and social responsibility:

Teachers, especially those working with children, should experience a sense of social and moral responsibility. This responsibility ensures the development of transversal competencies, such as mutual respect, cooperation and teamwork.

Psychological and pedagogical training:

Psychological and pedagogical training of teachers is important. This, in turn, helps to develop management skills, motivation, self-awareness and communication.

Development of management and problem-solving skills:

The goal of the course is to prepare future teachers to solve various problems arising in their work, to use innovative methods and to teach them the necessary skills of effective management.

In these days, the development of pedagogical conditions and modern pedagogical approaches create great opportunities for the successful development of professional transversal competencies of future teachers.

RESULTS

Professional transversal competencies involve developing the skills and qualifications of individuals preparing for teaching and educational activities. “Transversal competencies” are general skills that help you succeed in various fields. Examples include:

1. Critical thinking — the ability to analyze problems and make effective decisions.
2. Teamwork — the ability to work with others to achieve goals.
3. Social and cultural sensitivity — the ability to adapt to and understand different social and cultural conditions.
4. Self-management — emotional stability and stress management, as well as proper time management.

5. Computer technology and digital competence — the ability to effectively use technology.

The scientific and pedagogical foundations for developing these competencies are based on the following:

1. The role of teachers in the learning process is to teach future teachers various pedagogical methods and to promote their personal and professional development.

2. Methodological approaches - the use of innovative teaching methods, such as problem-based learning, active learning, interactive methods and other modern pedagogical technologies.

3. Formation of practical skills - involving students in practical activities, modeling various situations and learning based on experience.

4. Individualization of learning - development of individual approaches to meet the needs of each student.

5. Pedagogical ethics and professional responsibility - teach teachers to understand professional ethics and morality, as well as their responsibility in society.

These approaches will help future teachers become highly qualified, competitive and successful professionals.

CONCLUSION AND DISCUSSION

In conclusion, it should be noted that the development of professional transversal competencies of future teachers is an integral part of the pedagogical process, and its effective implementation directly affects the development of society. The pedagogical conditions existing today create sufficient opportunities for improving the qualifications of teaching staff, training them in modern pedagogical knowledge and skills. However, for further development of teachers' competencies, it is necessary to actively use systematic and continuous education, methodological approaches, modern technologies and innovative pedagogical methods.

At the same time, important factors in increasing the effectiveness of pedagogical conditions created for professional development are cooperation between teachers, parents and the public, as well as strengthening the material base of educational institutions. Also, when forming the professional competencies of teachers, special attention should be paid to improving their socio-psychological and communication skills.

It is necessary to create important pedagogical conditions for the effective development of professional transversal competencies of future teachers, improving the education system in the future, ensuring social progress in society. This can be achieved through the modernization of pedagogical activity, the development of new methods, and improving the professional skills of teachers.

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